

CHRONIC NICOTINE POISONING AND ITS IMPACT ON GASTRIC MUCOSA: DETOXIFICATION METHODS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14557680>

Abstract

Chronic nicotine poisoning causes significant morphological changes in the gastric mucosa, such as erosions, ulcers, hyperemia, and hypertrophy. This study examines the impact of nicotine on the gastric mucosa and evaluates the effectiveness of detoxification methods in restoring mucosal integrity. The results demonstrate that detoxification therapy significantly reduces inflammation, improves mucosal condition, and alleviates clinical symptoms. This study highlights the importance of early diagnosis and comprehensive treatment for patients suffering from chronic nicotine poisoning and provides a basis for developing new therapeutic strategies.

Keywords:

Chronic nicotine poisoning, gastric mucosa, erosions, ulcers, hyperemia, detoxification, restoration, gastropathy.

Relevance Chronic nicotine poisoning is one of the leading causes of gastric disorders, leading to damage to the gastric mucosa. Nicotine causes pathological changes such as erosions, ulcers, and hyperemia, which can progress to more severe diseases, including chronic gastritis and peptic ulcers. Understanding how nicotine affects the gastric mucosa and the methods that can effectively aid in restoring its structure and function is crucial. Detoxification plays an essential role in treating patients with chronic nicotine poisoning, as it helps eliminate toxins and reduce inflammation. Developing effective treatment approaches and preventive measures for nicotine-induced gastric diseases is vital for improving patient health and preventing long-term complications. This study aims to explore the mechanisms behind nicotine-induced gastric damage and evaluate the effectiveness of detoxification therapies in treating such conditions.

Objective

The objective of this study is to examine the impact of chronic nicotine poisoning on the gastric mucosa and assess the effectiveness of detoxification methods in restoring the damaged mucosal structure. The study aims to identify morphological changes such as erosions, ulcers, hyperemia, and hypertrophy, and analyze the clinical symptoms, including pain, heartburn, and nausea. The

expected results will help develop effective treatment and prevention strategies for gastric diseases caused by chronic nicotine poisoning and improve patients' quality of life.

Materials and Methods The study included 100 patients with chronic nicotine poisoning, divided into two groups: the first group received detoxification therapy, while the second group received standard treatment. All participants underwent fiberoptic gastroduodenoscopy to assess the condition of the gastric mucosa. Morphological changes such as erosions, ulcers, hyperemia, and hypertrophy were identified. Detoxification therapy included nicotine and toxin removal agents, along with antisecretory drugs aimed at restoring the mucosal lining and reducing inflammation.

Results (Fiberoptic gastroduodenoscopy revealed that patients who received detoxification therapy had less severe morphological changes in the gastric mucosa compared to those receiving standard treatment. In the first group, fewer erosions (60.3% vs. 42.9%) and ulcers (48.3% vs. 35.7%) were observed. Hyperemia was found in 69% of patients in the first group and 71.4% in the second group. The first group also had fewer fibrinous plaques (25.9% vs. 19%). These findings indicate the positive effects of detoxification therapy in reducing the pathological changes in the gastric mucosa.

Conclusion The study confirms that chronic nicotine poisoning leads to significant morphological changes in the gastric mucosa, including erosions, ulcers, and hyperemia. Detoxification therapy significantly improves the condition of the mucosa, reducing inflammation and alleviating clinical symptoms. The results suggest that detoxification should be an integral part of treatment for patients with chronic nicotine poisoning. By restoring mucosal integrity, detoxification therapy helps prevent further complications, improves overall health, and shortens recovery time. Early diagnosis and targeted treatment are essential for managing the gastric disorders induced by chronic nicotine exposure, and detoxification plays a crucial role in patient recovery.

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